

AROUND AN UNPRECEDENTED CORRESPONDENCE BETWEEN HEITOR VILLA-LOBOS AND MARGUERITE LONG⁷

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Abstract: The private collection of French pianist Marguerite Long (1874-1966), owned by the Médiathèque Musical Mahler in Paris, has an extensive archive which contains a significant collection of correspondence received from a large number of personalities. This collection includes three letters in French, written by the Brazilian composer Heitor Villa-Lobos, sent to the renowned pianist: two of them dated 1952, typed and another entirely handwritten and undated. This article, result of an ongoing research, intends to transcribe, translate and think about this brief but revealing correspondence.

Keywords: Heitor Villa-Lobos. Marguerite Long. correspondence. *Médiathèque Musical Mahler*. Piano.

⁷ This work was presented in a first format - in Portuguese - at the VI Symposium Villa-Lobos (2021) organized by the University of São Paulo – USP.

According to Cecília Dunoyer de Segonzac, biographer of Marguerite Long (1874-1966), the country with which the renowned French pianist established the closest ties was Brazil⁸. Proof of this is the correspondence received from various personalities in the Brazilian music scene found in the private collection of Marguerite Long, owned by *the Médiathèque Musical Mahler*⁹ in Paris.

Influential in the international musical and pianistic environment, we find in this impressive collection approximately 850 letters sent by important names, among which Maurice Ravel, Claude Debussy, Emma Debussy, Gabriel Fauré, Isaac Albeniz, Jacques Ibert, Vincent d'Indy, Alfred Cortot, Jacques Durand, Max Eschig, Darius Milhaud, Erik Satie, Florent Schmitt, Arthur Honegger, Roland Manuel, Ida Rubinstein, George Enesco, Dimitri Chostakovitch, Jacques Thibaud, Dinu Lipatti, Sergiu Celibidache, Emil Gilels, Reynaldo Hahn, Paul Badura-Skoda, Van Cliburn, Blanche Selva, Carlo Zecchi, Aldo Ciccolini and many others. There are also approximately 100 unidentified letters, 66 postcards and 36 business letters. Among the Brazilian names that we find in the midst of this extraordinary correspondence, it is worth mentioning Eleazar de Carvalho, Guilherme Fontainha, José Kliass (Russia/Brazil), Souza Lima, Homero de Magalhães, Anna-Stella Schic, Magda Tagliaferro and Heitor Villa-Lobos.

The present article thus intends to transcribe, translate and reflect on a brief correspondence (3 letters) collected in the mentioned collection, written by the Brazilian composer Heitor Villa-Lobos (1887-1959) and addressed to the French pianist Marguerite Long.

Through this correspondence, it is possible to confirm the complicity and bonds of friendship between the two, as well as a close musical collaboration that began in the twenties when, during his second French season (1927-30), Villa-Lobos composed the cycle for piano solo *Francette et Pià* (1929), a work he dedicated to the children's class of Marguerite Long's *Conservatoire National de Paris*.

The seasons spent in Paris were decisive in Villa-Lobos' path. And, in the 1950s (period to which the correspondence in focus refers), after the two great periods spent in the French

⁸Cecília Dunoyer de Segonzac, *Marguerite Long 1874-1966, un siècle de vie musicale française*, Paris, Findakly, 1993, p.268.

⁹Sincere thanks to the Médiathèque Musical Mahler for making available all the documentation that integrates the private archive of the French pianist Marguerite Long and necessary for the realization of the present study.

capital (1923-24 and 1927-30), the name of the Brazilian composer in France was recognized and respected. Consequently, important names in the French musical scene become part of his network of relationships, including Darius Milhaud, Maurice Ravel, Florent Schmitt and Marguerite Long. In the study carried out by the French researcher Anaïs Fléchet, *Villa-Lobos à Paris*¹⁰, it is possible to understand the dimension and importance that these long periods spent in France represented for the international recognition of the work of Heitor Villa-Lobos.

Thus, part of the private collection of the pianist Marguerite Long, owned by *Médiathèque Musical Mahler*, are three letters in French, two of them dated 1952, typed and one entirely handwritten and undated.

The first of them sent from Rio de Janeiro on August 2, 1952 provides us with a great deal of information. Villa-Lobos begins the letter by expressing his sadness at the impossibility of Marguerite Long coming to Brazil at that time and at the treatment (a hand problem) that the pianist was undergoing.

Marguerite Long would come to Brazil twice, both at the invitation of Heitor Villa-Lobos (FLÉCHET, 2004, p. 110). The first in 1932, and as Anaïs Fléchet points out, this was the occasion to promote exclusively contemporary French music. She holds a series of lectures and interpretation courses dedicated to the French school, an opportunity to interpret works by well-known French composers, but also by composers less known to the Brazilian public, such as “Emmanuel Chabrier, Florent Schmitt, Gabriel Pierné, Jacques Ibert, Marcel Delannoy and Francis Poulenc” (FLÉCHET, 2004, p. 110). The second trip - which is depicted in the first letter of the series in question - , which took place in 1954, proves the maturing of the bonds of friendship between Long and Villa, but also between Brazil, since their performances would not be solely focused on music French, but also to the interest and importance of this “Franco-Brazilian” cultural exchange. Proof of this is the dossier “Voyage au Brésil” held by the Marguerite Long archive¹¹, where we find a series of documents related to that 1954 trip to Brazil. Among them, the reception speech to the Academy of Fine Arts of Rio de Janeiro: “Music, where the soul of a people can be freely expressed, occupies a fundamental place; and it is in this sense that I am happy to be able to make my modest contribution in an ever more intense search for a Franco-Brazilian cultural community.”¹² (LONG, 1954)

¹⁰Anaïs Fléchet, *Villa-Lobos à Paris*. Paris: L'Harmattan, 2004.

¹¹Fonds Marguerite Long, Paris: *Médiathèque Musical Mahler*.

¹²Fonds Marguerite Long, *Discours de réception à l'Académie des Beaux-Arts de Rio de Janeiro*, 08/1954, Paris: *Médiathèque Musical Mahler*.

Still regarding the first letter of the series, Villa expresses his gratitude for the dissemination of his work in France, which he considered his “Homeland of the Soul” and adds:

Here is the list of works that you could make your excellent artists play and that I am infinitely grateful for:
CIRANDAS (16 pieces) – I WILL SEND YOU THE COPIES
BABY'S OFFSPRING N.1 (8 PIECES) - MAX-ESCHIG
RUDEPOEMA – MAX ESCHIG

It is important to point out that the works mentioned had their premieres in Paris in the 1920s, that is, in a way, these works had already been circulating in the international music scene for three decades. The Polish pianist Arthur Rubinstein (1887-1982) – an important promoter of Villa's pianistic work - would be responsible for the premieres of *Prole do Bebê n.1* on May 30, 1924, in a concert organized at the *Salle des Agriculteurs*, a period that coincides with the end of Villa-Lobos's first season in Paris, as well as the monumental *Rudepoema*, in the historic concert held at *Salle Gaveau* on October 24, 1927, a period that coincides with the beginning of the second Parisian season of the Brazilian composer.

Below is the full translation of the letter from Heitor Villa-Lobos sent to Marguerite Long dated August 2, 1952. The transcription in the original language is attached.

H. Villa-Lobos

Rua Araújo Porto Alegre, 56 – Apt. 54
Rio de Janeiro
Brazil

Rio de Janeiro, August 2, 1952¹³

My dear friend,

Your two letters of the 23rd and 26th of July brought us great sadness for depriving us of the great joy of having our great Friend and our great Artist here.

I fully understand the difficulties caused by the delay in all the procedures and I hope that at a next opportunity everything will be arranged more quickly and that your finger, after the treatment will be immediately healed and our Marguerite Long will have the opportunity to receive all the honors that she deserves. well deserves.

Thank you very much for your great kindness in giving a conference about me in France, where I consider my Homeland of the Soul, and in the next few days Mindinha will send you documents about me.

Here is the list of works that you could make your excellent artists play and that I am infinitely grateful for:
CIRANDAS (16 pieces) – I WILL SEND YOU THE COPIES

¹³Entirely typed letter containing only the handwritten signature.

BABY'S OFFSPRING N.1 (8 PIECES) - MAX-ESCHIG
RUDEPOEMA – MAX ESCHIG

I have just sent your letter to the Minister of Foreign Affairs,
Ambassador João Neves da Fontoura, who was very pleased with your
kindness,

My ballet “RUDA” will be presented at the Teatro Scala in Milan in
April, and I am looking forward to the copy of the recording that your
student Daniel Weinberg [sic ¹⁴] made and sent to Minister Labieno Salgado,
Consulate of Brazil in Paris.

Hoping for the great pleasure of seeing you soon and in full health, the
two friends cordially embrace her.

friend ever,
Villa-Lobos¹⁵

The second letter in the series, written the following month, was also sent from Rio de Janeiro, dated September 22, 1952 and sent to Marguerite Long in Italy. The letter confirms that the pianist's trip to Brazil was not carried out that year, a trip that, as discussed earlier, would take place two years later. Villa still comments on the recovery of her friend's hand and informs that she would soon be back in Paris. Below is the full translation of the letter from Heitor Villa-Lobos sent to Marguerite Long dated September 22, 1952. The transcription in the original language is attached.

H. Villa-Lobos

Rua Araújo Porto Alegre, 56 – Apt. 54
Rio de Janeiro
Brazil

Rio de Janeiro, September 22, 1952¹⁶

Mrs. MARGUERITE LONG
SAN ANGELO 3832
VENEZIA – ITALY

My dear friend,

Your letter of September 3 touched us with the word so affectionate in Portuguese - SAUDADES. [sic]

Mindy and I hope with all our hearts that you are fully recovered and that our great regret at not being lucky enough to have you here as we so wished may make up for it if your finger is in good shape.

¹⁴Daniel Wayenberg (1929-2019), Finnish pianist and composer. Student of Marguerite Long from 1947 onwards. We did not find any reference to the recording mentioned by Villa-Lobos in the letter in question.

¹⁵Heitor Villa-Lobos. [Mail]: Recipient: Marguerite Long. Rio de Janeiro, August 2, 1952. Paris: *Mediathèque Musical Mahler*, Fonds Marguerite Long.

¹⁶Entirely typed letter containing only the handwritten signature.

Forget about the finger altogether, and especially now that you've healed it.

Restart the exercises I advised you in Paris, and everything will go well as we wish.

Until today we are very sorry that your trip to Brazil was not possible this year, but we are sure that we will have this happy opportunity soon.

We are due to arrive in Paris in the first half of March, and it will be a great joy for both of us to see you very cheerful, happy and in perfect health.

We embrace you very cordially,

H. Villa-Lobos¹⁷

The third letter in the series is entirely handwritten and undated; however, we understand that it would be later than the previous ones, according to the reflections that follow. In this brief letter it is possible to perceive the empathetic personality of Villa-Lobos. In it, the composer presents and recommends the Brazilian pianist Yara Bernette (1920-2002) to Marguerite Long and intercedes for her.

According to Anaïs Fléchet, “the end of the 1940s as well as the beginning of the 1950s saw the arrival of a new generation of Brazilian musicians in Paris” (FLÉCHET, 2004, p. 111). We observe in the testimony, and in the production of some of them, the gratitude towards the composer who sought through his network of relationships to open doors in the French scene for many Brazilian interpreters.

Pianist Anna-Stella Schic¹⁸(1922-2009) arrived in Paris in 1947 and, recommended by Villa-Lobos, joined Marguerite Long's piano class. In an interview with Alain Cochard, on the occasion of the 40th anniversary of the composer's death, Anna-Stella gives a long account of the music and her relationship with Villa:

(...) “it was in France, when I was a student, that solid bonds of friendship were consolidated between us. The consul general of Brazil was a personal friend of Villa-Lobos and one day he introduced me to him. (...) In the program of the recital that I played in 1952 at Salle Gaveau, I included the Brazilian Cycle (in its European premiere), one of the most magnificent works for the piano, and I had the happiness of working on this score with him, as well as as well as other works, such as the 2nd ^{Concerto} – which I also held the first European audition in the same year in Paris, under his direction.” (In: PIANO, 1998-99, p. 98)

¹⁷Heitor Villa-Lobos, Ibid. 09/22/1952.

¹⁸Between the years 1976-77 Anna-Stella Schic recorded for EMI ODEON, at Salle Wagram, in Paris, the complete version for solo piano by Heitor Villa-Lobos. The work was considered by French critics among the best productions of the year (1980) and received the “Diapason d'Or” seal. In Brazil, the integral was distributed by Estúdio Eldorado in the 1980s.

The pianist Homero de Magalhães ¹⁹(1924-1997) also expresses his gratitude in a long report available in his doctoral thesis “The pianistic work of Heitor Villa Lobos” (UNESP, 1994):

I had the honor of being a protégé of Villa-Lobos. (...) One of the best memories I have of him comes from 1956. At that time, I was a scholarship holder in Vienna and while passing through Paris, I needed a recommendation from President Juscelino Kubitschek because my scholarship was threatened with being cut. I went to visit the Maestro who received me early in his room at the Hotel de Bedford, (...). I explained my business and the Maestro immediately dictated to Mindinha a telegram to the President on my matter. (MAGALHÃES, 1994, p.6)

And still:

My career was, from the beginning, linked to the work of the great composer: In 1957, at the *Cité Universitaire* in Paris, I participated in the concert commemorating the 70th anniversary of Villa-Lobos, performing in the presence of the Master, Suite 1913 for piano and orchestra and I witnessed the ovation he received from a room full of students, professors and authorities from various countries. (MAGALHÃES, 1994, p.110)

The letter in focus here confirms Villa's desire to promote young compatriots who, like him, sought in the French capital a way to consolidate their careers. Thus, it is possible to suggest an approximate period for the letter in question, since the debut of pianist Yara Bernette would take place in Europe in 1955, when she played the *Bachianas Brasileiras* n.3 with the Paris Conservatory Orchestra conducted by Heitor Villa -Lobos ²⁰. The letter also leads us to understand a possible collaboration by Marguerite Long for the realization of this premiere with the National Conservatory Orchestra, the institution in which the French pianist worked.

Below is the full translation of the letter in question, sent by Heitor Villa-Lobos to Marguerite Long. In the annexes the transcription in the original language.

My illustrious dear friend,

Anticipating a little the personal visit I hope to make in a few months, I would like to introduce and recommend Yara Bernette, a remarkable Brazilian pianist (from S. Paulo) already consecrated before the Brazilian and American public with great success.

She wants to receive from you your precious advice as an incomparable master and at the same time an orientation on how she should start her artistic career in Europe.

¹⁹Pianist and teacher Homero de Magalhães was a great supporter of Villa-Lobos' pianistic work. He made several recordings, conferences and courses dedicated to the composer's pianistic work. The first Brazilian version of the complete cycle of the 16 *Cirandas* (1960) stands out. He says: With this recording I obtained several awards, including the National Record Award, (...)” (MAGALHÃES, 1994, p.11).

²⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Yara_Bernette#cite_note-MM-4

Confident of your good reception, I have the great pleasure of thanking you cordially, and renewing, dear and distinguished friend, the sentiments of my deep esteem and great respect,

Signed by: Villa-Lobos

Figure 1: Villa-Lobos Museum. Heitor Villa-Lobos and Marguerite Long, 1957.

Attachments

Transcription of the 3 letters of ownership of the *Fonds Marguerite Long* sent by the Brazilian composer Heitor Villa-Lobos to the French pianist. The *Fonds Marguerite Long* is owned by the *Médiathèque Musicale Mahler* in Paris.

Letter n.1

H. Villa-Lobos

Rua Araújo Porto Alegre, 56 – Apt. 54
Rio de Janeiro
Brazil

Rio de Janeiro, 2 Août 1952²¹

Ma très chere Amie,

Votre [sic] deux lettres du 23 et 26 Juillet nous a donné beaucoup de tristesse de nous priver de la grande joie d'avoir ici notre grande Amie et notre grande Artiste.

J'ai bien compris les difficultés à cause du retard de toutes les démarches et j'espère que dans le prochaine opportunité toute [sic] pourra être arrangé plus vite et que le votre doigt, après le traitement will be immédiatement guéri et que notre Marguerite Long aura l'occasion de recevoir toutes les honneurs qu'elle bien mérite.

Merci beaucoup pour votre si grande gentillesse de faire une conférence sur moi en France, où je considère ma Patrie d'Âme, et dans quelques jours Mindinha vous enverra des documents sur moi.

Voilà [sic] la liste des oeuvres que vous pourrez faire jouez vos excellents artistes et que je vous remercie infiniment:

CIRANDAS (16 morceaux) – JE VOUS ENVERREZ LES COPIES

BABY'S OFFSPRING N.1 (8 morceaux) – MAX-ESCHIG

RUDEPOEMA – MAX ESCHIG

Je viens de remettre votre lettre au Ministre des Affaires, Ambassadeur João Neves da Fontoura, qui a été très content de votre amabilité, [sic]

Mon ballet “RUDA” will be donné au Theater Scala de Milano dans le mois d'Avril, et j'espère ancieux la cotype de la engraving que votre grand elève Daniel Weinberg [sic] a fait et aussi aura déjà envoyé au Ministre Labienno Salgado, Consulat du Brasil to Paris.

En attendant le plus grand plaisir de vous revoir très bientôt et dans [sic] pleine santé, les deux amis vous embrassent très cordialement.

²¹Entirely typed letter containing only the handwritten signature.

L'ami de toujours,
Villa-Lobos

Figure 2 : Letter from Heitor Villa-Lobos to Marguerite Long.
Paris: *Mediathèque Musical Mahler* , Fonds Marguerite Long.

Letter n. two

H. Villa-Lobos

Rua Araújo Porto Alegre, 56 – Apt. 54
Rio de Janeiro
Brazil

Rio de Janeiro, 22 September 1952²²

Mrs. MARGUERITE LONG
SAN ANGELO 3832
VENEZIA – ITALY

Ma très chere Amie,

Votre lettre du 3 Septembre nous a touché avec le mot si affectueux en portugais-SAUDADES. [sic]

Mindinha et moi espérons [sic] de tout nos coeurs, qui vous avez complètement rétablie et qui notre grand regret de n'avoir pas la chance de vous avoir ici comme nous avons bien désiré, puisse compenser si votre doigt est déjà en bonne forme.

Oubliez le doigt complètement, et surgeut maintenant qui vous avez le soigné. Recommencez [sic] les exercices qui j'ai vous conseillé à Paris, et toute [sic] sera bien comme nous vous souhaitons.

Jusu'aujourd'hui [sic] nous regrettons beaucoup qui n'était pas possible cet année votre Voyage au Brésil, mais nous sommes sûres [sic] qui nous aurons cette heureuse opportunité très bientôt.

Nous devons arriver à Paris la première quinzaine [sic] de Mars, et sera pour nous deux une grande joie vous rencontrer très gaie, heureuse et en parfaite santé.

Nous vous embrassons très cordialement,

H. Villa-Lobos

²²Entirely typed letter containing only the handwritten signature.

Letter n.3

Mon illustre et chère amie ²³,

En anticipant à peu la visite personnelle que j'espère vous faire dans quelques mois, je voudrais vous présenter et vous recommander [sic] Yara Bernette, notable pianiste brésilienne (from S. Paulo) qui a déjà été consacrée devant le public brésilien et américain avec grand succès.

Elle désire recevoir de vous, vos précieux conseils de maître incomparable et au même temps une orientation sur la façon dans laquelle elle devra initier sa carrière artistique en Europe.

Certain de votre bon accueil, j'ai la vive satisfaction de vous remercier cordialement, et renouveler, chère et illustre amie, les sentiments de ma profonde estime et de mon grand respect.

Signé for : Villa-Lobos

References

DUNOYER DE SEGONZAC, Cecilia. *Marguerite Long 1874-1966, un siècle de vie musicale française*, Paris, Fayard, 1993.

FLÉCHET, Anais. *Villa-Lobos à Paris*. Paris: L'Harmattan, 2004.

LONG, Marguerite. *Discours de réception à l'Académie des Beaux-Arts in Rio de Janeiro*. Paris: Médiathèque Musical Mahler, Fonds Marguerite Long, 1954, 10 p. handwritten + 5 p. typed.

MAGALHÃES, Homero. *The pianistic work of Heitor Villa-Lobos*. São Paulo: Doctoral Thesis (UNESP), 1994.

VILLA-LOBOS, Heitor. *Francette et Pià*. Recherche et compilation par Gérard Hugon. Paris: Max Eschig, 2007.

_____. [Mail]: Recipient: Marguerite Long. Rio de Janeiro, August 2, 1952. Paris: Médiathèque Musical Mahler, Fonds Marguerite Long.

_____. [Mail]: Recipient: Marguerite Long. Rio de Janeiro, September 22, 1952. Paris: Médiathèque Musical Mahler, Fonds Marguerite Long.

_____. [Mail]: Recipient: Marguerite Long. Not dated. Paris: Médiathèque Musical Mahler, Fonds Marguerite Long.

SCHIC, Anna-Stella. *Souvenirs de l'Indien Blanc*. Propos recueillis par Alain Cochard. In: PIANO, Hors series. Paris: 1998-99, p. 98.

²³Undated and entirely handwritten letter .